

Selective Monitoring Using Performance Metric Predicates

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Abstract

The field of parallel processing is going through an important evolution in technology characterized by a significant increase in the number of processors within such systems. As the number of processors increases, the conventional techniques for monitoring the performance of parallel systems will produce large amounts of data in the form of event trace files. The authors propose one possible solution to this data size problem: Performance Metric Predicates. These predicates permit the user to define performance parameters that control the output of event trace data during the application's execution time. The authors assert that the use of Performance Metric Predicates provides a powerful and useful tool for the control of event trace data output from large complex systems.

1 Introduction

Recently, there has been significant growth in the number of performance monitoring and visualization tools developed for parallel processing systems. These tools have proven themselves valuable in the analysis of performance behavior of parallel algorithms. Although the sources for such tools are varied and their styles diverse, many of these tools possess similar characteristics that present serious problems when they are used on Grand Challenge[1] magnitude problems. Such Grand Challenge problems demand parallel systems with an ever increasing number of processors. As the number of processors in parallel systems increases, the conventional performance monitoring techniques of the current tools will produce huge and unmanageable amounts of data in the form of trace files. Our experience has shown that monitoring the performance of even simple applications running on relatively small numbers of processors generates large event trace record files.

Figure 1: AIMS Trace File Sizes for 8, 16, 32, and 64 Processors

Figure 1 shows the AIMS [2] trace file sizes¹ for a parallelized version of ARC2D[4] charted in relation to the number of processors. Two important points worth noting in this figure are that the trace files represented here monitor performance for an execution time of less than two seconds (production runs will likely run significantly longer) and the monitored executions use, at most, only 64 processors.

Large amounts of trace data make it difficult for programmers to identify the areas causing performance degradation when using existing performance visualization tools.² The authors contend that programmers have a good understanding of the *symptoms* of performance degradation (e.g., bad node utilization, excessive blocking); the mark of an effective tool is

¹ The AIMS monitor is quite similar to PICL[3] but presents slightly more detailed data. Calculations have shown that AIMS file sizes are approximately 30% larger than PICL file sizes.

² In addition, this unnecessary monitoring increases the perturbation of the application since flushing large amounts of data can affect the pattern of computation.

how quickly it helps them identify the *cause* of this degradation. Experience has shown that most of the computation proceeds within the expected norms of performance. Programmers are typically only interested in seeing program behavior when the program failed to perform its tasks efficiently. By intelligently choosing which performance data to save, and thus, ultimately present, tools can focus the user's attention on areas of interest within the execution.

In this paper, the authors propose extensions to existing software monitors that follow the inserted event recorder paradigm [5]. We advocate the adoption of user-defined Performance Metric Predicates (PMPs). These predicates control the output of trace data based on a user-defined metric of program efficiency. The PMPs test the state of program performance; if the performance does not fall within specified tolerances, the monitor will output the performance history leading up to the point of performance degradation. Below are some simple PMP specifications:

- Idle time more than 55% of total run time.
- Time spent within global synchronization is less than 10 milliseconds.
- Time spent waiting for a single message is less than 40 milliseconds.

2 Implementation

The Performance Metric Predicate Library (PMPL) is an extension to a standard event trace monitor such as AIMS or PICL. The only modification to a *standard* performance monitoring library required by PMPL is that the monitor store its event records in a cyclic queue. This is in contrast to the usual linear buffer that is maintained by AIMS and PICL. This cyclic queue holds the event records for the recent performance history of the node.

Figure 2 illustrates the implementation of PMPL for the AIMS system. Note that the shaded portion of this structure is representative of most software performance monitors, which employ inserted event recorders [5] (with the exception of the use of a cyclic queue). In most monitors of this type, the instrumented application generates a record for each monitored event. These records are stored within the monitor's event buffer. In the modified system, however, after the record is stored into the monitor's queue, it is passed to PMPL. During this stage, PMPL evaluates the record with respect to the user-defined performance metrics. The result is then checked against

user-defined tolerances and the trace output enable state is set accordingly.

If the system is not already in a trace output enable state and performance tolerances have been exceeded, the node broadcasts a signal to all other nodes. Thus, a trace output enable state is established and the nodes write the contents of their cyclic queues to the system disk. This selective flush of trace event records provides a recent history of the events leading up to the point where tolerances were exceeded. From these event records, performance visualization tools may reconstruct the state of the system from a point leading up to and beyond the time performance degradation occurred.

Once in a trace enable output state, the system flushes the contents of its event buffer each time it cycles until the state is disabled. The trace output disable state is entered only if the following conditions are met:

- All of the nodes of the system are within the tolerances that were exceeded to cause this current phase of trace output.
- Each node must go through one full queue cycle without any tolerances being exceeded.

3 Results

To demonstrate the usefulness of Performance Metric Predicates the authors chose a version of the ARC2D parallel benchmark[4] that uses pipelined Gaussian Elimination. This application was chosen because it is made up of clearly defined phases of computation. In our test, we ran a single iteration of ARC2D on an 8, 16, 32 and 64 processor iPSC/860. In each of these runs, the AIMS performance monitor was used with a single Performance Metric Predicate defined. This PMP defined a tolerance for waiting on message receives between 10 milliseconds and 17 milliseconds. In other words, trace output will be enabled if any node of the system waits to receive a message for 17 milliseconds or more and trace output will be disabled when the receive wait time goes back down below 10 milliseconds for one complete cycle of the monitor's queue.

In every run of ARC2D, one particular phase of the computation consistently exceeded these defined performance tolerances; the "reduction" phase. Figure 3 illustrates the *pipelining* behavior of this phase and its effect upon the system's performance with the AIMS Grid view. This figure shows the passing of results

Figure 2: AIMS augmented with PMPL

from one row of processors to the next. Eventually, the *wave* of data flows downwards in the given view and then flows back up to the top row again. This method exhibits bad utilization because the top row waits for a long time for the data to make its way back. These symptoms of long message queues and long message wait times make this an area of interest for programmers who are attempting to determine the performance characteristics of their code. With the above PMP installed, visualization tools are able to produce displays very similar (in some cases, identical) to ones generated by a complete event dump.

Figure 4 presents a graph that compares the original AIMS trace file size with the trace file size with the PMP described above enable. This chart shows that by focusing on the problematic phases of the monitored application, a significant savings in event trace output may be realized. It is especially noteworthy that this savings increases with the number of nodes. This is largely due to runs with large numbers of processor requiring much more complex (and lengthy) initialization sequences.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

The authors have demonstrated that the use of Performance Metric Predicates can be an effective means of controlling the size of event trace files during the run time of a parallel application. By wisely selecting levels of performance tolerance, the user may focus the output of event recorder monitors on specific areas of an application based on performance behavior. This tool for selective monitoring promises to be very useful in controlling the size of performance monitor event trace data for complex programs running on large systems.

Although this approach of controlling trace file output shows some promise, several technical challenges to the use of Performance Metric Predicates still exist. Three such important areas of concern are:

- The additional perturbation to the application's performance imposed by the implementation of Performance Metric Predicates. Although PMPs promise to decrease the total output of event trace data coming from a monitored system, PMPs may cause more frequent smaller flushes of trace data. This increase in the frequency of event trace

Figure 3: AIMS Grid View: reduction phase of ARC2D

Figure 4: AIMS vs. PMPL Trace File Sizes

flushes may cause a significant perturbation to the application's performance.

- Effective synchronization of all nodes of the system both during and after a trace enable output phase also presents technical challenges in avoiding deadlock.
- The ability to accurately reconstruct the very fine grain state of each node of the monitored system at a given time. The PMPL can maintain a checkpoint of each local node's state during run time. These checkpoints may be read by visualization and analysis tools in order to reconstruct the state of the system for any given time. However, some data required to give a truly accurate checkpoint of the system's state may be discerned only from a global perspective of each node's state.

Future work on Performance Metric Predicates will focus on providing practical solutions to these three stated technical challenges. In addition, work with PMPs will continue with more complex applications running on larger systems.

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